

Liver-centric multi-organ-chip approaches for safety and efficacy

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Abstract

In the last decade, the improvement of systems, including 3D culture models and microphysiological systems (MPS), delineated a promising route to human-relevant in vitro testing by emulating biology in single- or multi-organ systems as a basis for fit-for-purpose assays. To enhance regulatory acceptance of these advanced non-animal test systems, it is necessary to increase the scientific credibility and confidence in the data generated. Microphysiological systems (MPS) have proven to be a powerful tool for recreating human tissue- and organ-like functions. Here in this talk we will concentrate on multi-organ-chip assays with liver as the central metabolizing organ utilized for safety and efficacy testing.